

4. M. N. ANSARI, M. G. JAIN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1023.
5. R. S. VERRMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 558.
6. M. N. ANSARI, M. G. JAIN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 909.
7. M. CALVIN and N. O. MELCHOIR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 8270.
8. BJERRUM, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haas and Son., Copenhagen, 1941.

A Dynamic TG Study of *Bis* (acetylacetonato)-Copper(II)

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THE thermal decomposition of *bis*(acetylacetonato)-copper(II), $[\text{Cu}(\text{acac})_2]$, has been studied by dynamic thermogravimetry. The compound has been reported to be stable and non-volatile¹ upto 191° and to decompose at higher temperatures in the absence of air to acac and metallic copper². In the present investigation carried out in static air, the residue left behind has been shown to be CuO by analysis. In this dynamic TG study, the fractional decomposition values (α s) were employed in studying the kinetics of the overall decomposition process by methods described elsewhere^{3,4,5}. Different functional forms of α , viz $f(\alpha)$ s, assumed to govern the rate controlling process, were chosen for obtaining

the $g(\alpha)$ values (where $g(\alpha) = \int_0^\alpha \frac{d\alpha}{f(\alpha)}$) from rate law

$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k f(\alpha)$. These $g(\alpha)$ values were used to evaluate

the kinetic parameters

Dynamic TG traces of the pure and dry complex (125 mg; mesh 200-240) prepared by known methods⁶ were obtained using 'Stanton' recording thermobalance (Model TR-1). The heating rate was 4° min⁻¹.

The TG trace redrawn as mass of sample versus temperature and the DTG curve are given in Fig. 1. The temperature of inception, T_i , temperature of completion, T_c , and peak temperature of decomposition, T_p , are 463, 538 and 524°K respectively. Mass loss found for the decomposition (95 mg) at T_p was in excellent agreement with the theoretical requirement (94.6 mg). Plots were made, $g(\alpha)$ versus temperature, for different mechanistic models for the decomposition and are set out in Fig. 2. From the linear portion of such plots, (i.e. 5, 6 and 7 in the figure) the frequency factor, Z , activation energy E^* and entropy of activation ΔS^* were

Fig. 1. TG, DTG curves

○-TG, ●-DTG

Fig. 2. Mechanistic plots

$g(\alpha)$: $\Delta \alpha^2$, $\Delta \alpha + (1-\alpha) \ln(1-\alpha)$,
 $\square [1-(1-\alpha)^{1/2}]^2$, $\square [1-\frac{2}{3}\alpha] - (1-\alpha)^{3/2}$,
 $\circ -\ln(1-\alpha)$, $\bullet [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$,
 $\ominus [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/3}$, $\bullet 1-(1-\alpha)^{1/2}$, $\circ 1-(1-\alpha)^{1/3}$

calculated by methods described elsewhere^{4,7} and are presented in Table 1. Although three model

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS

Form of $f(\alpha)$	$g(\alpha)$	Frequency factor Z	Energy of activation, E^* (k. J. mole ⁻¹)
$(1-\alpha)$	$-\ln(1-\alpha)$	7.9×10^{10}	184.8
$2(1-\alpha) [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{1/2}$	5.6×10^8	64.9
$3(1-\alpha) [-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{2/3}$	$[-\ln(1-\alpha)]^{2/3}$	2.6×10^7	41.4

equations for $g(\kappa)$ viz. $-\ln(1-\kappa)$, $[-\ln(1-\kappa)]^{1/2}$ and $[-\ln(1-\kappa)]^{1/3}$ gave linear relations, only the one corresponding to the Mampel model equation⁹, i.e. $(1-\kappa)$ for $f(\kappa)$, gave reasonable values of frequency factor and activation energy. The order of magnitude of frequency factor according to this model equation is agreeably close to theoretical requirement⁹. The moderately negative entropy of activation ($-71 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$) indicates formation of an ordered transition state. It is likely that the complex decomposes by random nucleation, i.e. with formation of a nucleus on every particle.

References

1. R. G. CHARLES and M. A. PAWLIKOWSKI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 442.
2. J. VON HOENE, R. G. CHARLES and W. M. HICKAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, **62**, 1098.
3. J. SESTAK, A. BROWN, V. BIRAK and G. BERGGREN, in "Thermal Analysis", R. F. SCHWENKER, JR. and P. D. GARN (Eds.), Academic Press, New York, 1959, Vol. 2.
4. C. G. R. NAIR and P. M. MADHUSUDANAN, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1976, **14**, 973.
5. V. SETAVA and J. SESTAK, *Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **45**, 154.
6. D. N. SEN and N. THANKARAJAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, **6**, 746.
7. J. R. MACCALLUM and J. TANNER, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 1970, **6**, 1083.
8. K. L. MAMPSEL, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, **A187**, 235.
9. R. D. SHANNON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1964, **60**, 1902.

Studies on Schiff Bases of Veratraldehyde

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A survey of literature¹⁻³ showed that study of Schiff bases of veratraldehyde has not been carried out so far. It was, therefore, of interest to synthesize new Schiff bases derived from veratraldehyde. This paper describes the synthesis of veratraldehyde Schiff bases, their sodium borohydride reduction products, spectral studies of the

Schiff bases and their reduced products, and fungicidal activity of Schiff bases and the secondary amines.

The Schiff bases have been prepared in quantitative yields by condensing equimolar quantities of veratraldehyde and aromatic amines (aniline and substituted anilines) in toluene by azeotropic distillation of water formed during the reaction. The Schiff bases having *m*-NO₂ and *o*-OCH₃ groups are dark coloured thick oils.

The uv spectra of the Schiff bases give four absorption bands at 213, 235, 270 and 335 nm. It has been found that the absorption bands (band II at 235 nm and band IV at 335 nm) are sensitive to N-phenyl substitution while the other two bands (band I at 213 nm and band III at 270 nm) usually remain unaffected. Band at ~270 nm is the characteristic band of >C=N- as is shown by the fact that this band completely disappears on reduction of the >C=N- linkage with sodium borohydride. In ir, >C=N- absorption is observed at ~1625 cm⁻¹.

Reduction of veratraldehyde Schiff bases has been carried out with sodium borohydride in methanol at 60-65°. The use of higher temperature is partly required because of low solubility of the Schiff bases in methanol. The reduction is not possible in case of Schiff bases having hydroxyl group in the N-phenyl ring and it is suppressed in case of 3,4-dimethoxybenzal-*o*-anisidine because of steric hindrance.

A study of the spectra of the reduced products in conjugation with those of the parent Schiff bases reveals that the absorption bands assigned to >C=N- linkage (~270 nm) are absent in the spectra of the reduced products. The ir spectra of the dihydro products lack the absorption bands (~1625 cm⁻¹) assigned to >C=N-, but contain additional bands (3440-3420 cm⁻¹) due to NH group.

The Schiff bases and their reduced products as well as the uv spectra of the Schiff bases are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I—CHARACTERISTICS OF VERATRALDEHYDE SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR DIHYDRO PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	Substituent in N-phenyl ring	m.p. (°C) of		UV Spectra of the Schiff Bases of Veratraldehyde			
		Schiff Base	Dihydro Product	Band I MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band II MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band III MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)	Band IV MeOH λ _{max} (nm)(log e)
1.	H	83	92	218 (4.03)	235 (4.23)	268 (4.39)	335 (4.33)
2.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	116	87	209 (4.18)	—	270 (4.16)	337 (3.04)
3.	<i>p</i> -OH	99	110	210 (3.85)	281 (4.12)	267 (4.38)	345 (4.38)
4.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	126	137	211 (4.30)	242 (4.18)	269 (4.36)	350 (4.30)
5.	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	97	60	211 (4.30)	242 (4.16)	270 (4.44)	350 (4.40)
6.	<i>o</i> -OH	100	—	303 (4.53)	242 (4.32)	262 (3.34)	355 (3.84)
7.	<i>m</i> -OH	215	—	210 (4.24)	248 (4.28)	270 (4.31)	355 (3.83)
8.	<i>m</i> -Cl	80	123	211 (3.55)	—	268 (3.35)	330 (3.15)
9.	<i>p</i> -Cl	83	124	211 (3.45)	—	268 (4.37)	336 (4.21)
10.	<i>p</i> -Br	99	107	210 (4.34)	—	270 (4.44)	346 (4.23)
11.	<i>o</i> -OOH	oil	100	209 (4.21)	230 (4.10)	269 (4.40)	348 (4.20)
12.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	oil	141	—	—	268 (5.54)	—

All the melting points are uncorrected. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses and yields were excellent.